

**DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATION PROJECT MANAGEMENT
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Abstract: *This article discusses the development of an innovative project management system in enterprises.*

Key words: *Enterprise, production, economy, innovation, foreign experience, management system.*

Today, in our republic, the creation of freedoms and a favorable environment for entrepreneurial activities, open competition conditions and opportunities to achieve high economic interest strengthen the aspirations of entrepreneurs to introduce innovation projects in the organization, expansion and changes of their activities. This leads to a wider study of the essence of innovation in our country, the development of relations to the organization and financing of innovation activities. Therefore, finding a complete answer to the question of what innovation is is of great importance in correctly defining and organizing the attitude towards it. It is known that the transition from one quality to another requires resources (energy, time, finances, funds, etc.). In turn, the implementation of the innovation requires resources. The most important of these are investment (money) and time. The main organizer of innovation activity is investment (funds) and introduction of innovation. It leads to the formation of a novelty market. The market of investment capital, the introduction of innovation is formed as a market of pure competition.

In the world economy, there is a trend of imbalance between demand and supply of investments. Today, we are witnessing that the flow of investments is being actively directed from developed countries to the economies of developing countries. As a result, the share of direct investments in the economy of developing countries is increasing sharply.

In turn, the existence of many problems related to the improvement of investment efficiency remains one of the main factors determining the need to improve the management of investment projects.

At the moment, in world practice, it is important to optimize the mechanisms of attracting foreign investments and placing them in promising and high-tech sectors of the economy,

developing the practice of venture financing of investment projects at the national and regional level, increasing the attractiveness of the investment environment, and ensuring the mutual compatibility of financial management tools for investment activities. is earning.

In particular, special attention should be paid to issues such as the peculiarities of the organization of investment activities in the regions of our country, the organization of activities of regional venture funds in the financing of investment projects, the improvement of mechanisms for the allocation of syndicated loans in the financing of investment projects, and the improvement of the efficiency of the use of internal resources, including population savings, in the organization of investment activities. must Improving the method of syndicated lending of large investment projects by commercial banks requires strengthening the long-term resource base of banks. For this purpose, it is necessary to reduce the required reserve rates of the Central Bank for long-term deposits of commercial banks, and to place state-owned funds as long-term deposits in commercial banks that provide syndicated lending in the main sectors of the economy, and to attract funds by securitizing loans to high-performance projects. increases the possibilities of financing investment projects.

Динамика роста ключевых экономических показателей в сфере ИКТ 2016-2020гг.

Динамика роста объема услуг сферы «информации и связи» в ВДС в 2016-2020гг. (трлн. сум)

Динамика роста объема оказанных услуг по виду экономической деятельности «информация и связь» в 2016-2020гг. (трлн. сум)

Динамика изменения объема инвестиций в основной капитал по виду деятельности «информация и связь» в 2016-2020гг. (трлн. сум)

Показатели Узбекистана в международном «Индексе развития электронного правительства»

➤ Since the first years of independence, the investment policy

implemented in Uzbekistan has supported the priority areas for ensuring the independence of fuel, energy and grain, implementing structural changes in the economy, increasing the export potential and increasing the production of import-substituting products. -support, open door policy to attract foreign investments was focused on. The investment policy was based on the following principles:

- ☐ selective support of the most important sectors and areas of activity based on the established state priorities;
 - ☐ Sufficient support for socially important sectors (health, education, culture, etc.) in order to improve the standard of living of the population, prolong life, prevent sharp social stratification, and ensure the activation of consumer demand;
 - ☐ attraction of foreign investments to priority areas based on mutual interest;
 - ☐ redistribution of potential investment resources from trade and money market to industry;
 - ☐ increasing intellectual capital and scientific and technical potential due to the concentration of production capital by supporting scientific research, experimental design works, purchasing licenses for new techniques from abroad, forming large corporations capable of maintaining large laboratories;
 - ☐ supporting investment projects aimed at deep processing of agricultural products and mineral resources and bringing them to the level of competitiveness in the foreign market;
- ☐ providing investments for rapid development of production facilities designed to meet the needs of the population for food and consumer goods;
 - ☐ improvement of the legal framework that regulates the interaction of the participants of investment processes. For this purpose, it is necessary to pay great attention to the support of investment projects implemented by the state in these directions.

In conclusion, usually, not all investment projects have the same indicators. Some indicators may be highly positive in one project and vice versa in another project, and some indicators may have a lower value in one project than in another project. Having such (mutually

conflicting) information of projects specific to one field creates competition between them. Making investment decisions can be challenging, especially in competitive investment environments.

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